

Android vs IOS: Digital Wellbeing in Future and the Marketing Concerns

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Abstract

Day by day the investment in the online advertisement is increasing. The reach and dimensions of the digital platforms are rising as well. Here the major complications are related to human lives. A technology should always improve the human life rather than distracting it. The tech giants consider this threat as an opportunity and solving it by their new initiatives called Digital wellbeing by Google and Screentime by Apple. Here the researcher explaining it by the help of Secondary data sources and how it will affect the Digital marketers as well.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Marketing Concerns, Effects of Online advertisements, Digital Wellbeing

Introduction

Millennium starts with the emergence of world's most fascinating tech companies. Dot com bubble were already stated by the end of the century. Apple was just a youngster by 25 year old and Google was a just a 2 year old kid. In the early 2000 software industry were started growing, the major reason was the improvement in the reach of internet and its speed in various countries. Silicon Valley has witnessed the growth of these start up as well. Later we saw the rise of social media platforms and how it is affecting in human life. As software technology grows we saw the simultaneous growth in the hardware industry as well, we need to consider every tech revolution consists of hard ware and software technologies. After the successful reach of 2G services causes the innovation of revolutionary products named Smart phones. Smartphone industry was totally controlled by the major market share holders Nokia Corporation (Finland) and the Blackberry Ltd (Canada). These companies are coupled their own hardware and software in their products. So Nokia used Symbian OS and Blackberry used their own blackberry OS.

In 2007 Google revealed first ever android to the public. But they had to wait until 2008 to get it commercialized. HTC developed the first ever Android device named HTC dream on 23 September 2008. And in June 2007 Apple Inc. revealed introductory I phone 2G and a year later the iPhone 3G as well. Apple loaded their phone with UNIX based iOS. The influence and the advanced features of Android and iOS was totally a game changer in the smartphone industry.it was totally affected the sales of Nokia and Blackberry sales and the companies lost the market share as well. Google and Apple try to embed their supplementary services to their smartphone OS. Google wants to be a software giant in all aspects and the apple focused to create revolutionary products. So the google opted an open source policy in Android OS but Apple has gone for closed source license policy. Both the companies pumped billions of dollars into their Smartphone devices and the supporting services. The rest of the story was all about Apps!

Always an invention has two sides. One will be the core advantages and how it's improving human life the rest we can consider as the "side effects". Smartphones are fetching a lot of human hours by their feature-rich Applications. Applications are really a problem solver but at the same time, it is creating a laziness in human life. A study by Dr. Jayanti P Acharya (Department of community medicine, Bhaskar medical college Hyderabad, AP India) shows that 47.4% of College students (age 17-23) are lacking the concentration by the excessive use of smart phones. And the major finding was Expectedly, almost all the subjects (96.1%) possessed cell phones, and used the device for a greater part of the day. Headache was found to be the commonest symptom (51.47%) followed by irritability/anger (50.79%). Other common mental symptoms included lack of concentration and poor academic performance, insomnia, anxiety etc. Among physical symptoms –body aches (32.19%), eye strain (36.51%), digital thumb (13.8%) were found to be frequent. Accidents are caused due to cell phone driving.

Figure 1 Dr. Jayanti P Acharya's study report

A Software Problem Solver

According to the last I/O 2018 (Google's Annual conference). Google has introduced a new feature called Digital Wellbeing for android Users. It will be the dedicated settings for maintaining a good and healthy Digital life. But this feature will be available on the Latest version of Android (A.9.0 Pie) Similarly Apple also introduced Screen Time as a settings on iOS 12.0. Both the companies' features have the same set of goals. Screen time and Digital

wellbeing are providing the same set of features to the users but their implementations policies are bit different. Before the final comment, we need to consider Google's Digital Wellbeing is still in Beta stage.

Features

Figure 2 Dash Board and Notification Panel of Apple Screen Time (Left) and Google's Digital Wellbeing (Right)

- **Wind Down Vs Down Time**

Wind down is a feature in Google's Digital wellbeing.it is allow users to set a time limit for active hours and quite hours. That means user can able to set a time for sleep for example a user set wind time from 11 PM to 05 AM at this time Phone's screen will be on Grayscale and the profile will be switched to Do not disturb Mode. With this all setting in the do not disturb mode would be applicable as well. Similarly Apple has Downtime. There the screen will go to grayscale but user will get notification as the phone is switching to Downtime and do not disturb mode will be enforced.

- **App Timing and App limit time**

Here the user can set a daily time limit for each application installed on their devices. Android will disable the application after reaching the daily time quota. Also, convert app icon in grayscale. But Apple will inform the user that you are reached the daily time quota, here the user can decide whether he/she need to continue or not.

- **Category Wise List**

IOS Screen time will provide the category wise insights like how much time a user spent in Social Networking, Games, Entertainment etc. it will help a user to determine how much time he/she is focusing on what and where.

Functional Out Come

Apple and Google have two different philosophy in their digital wellbeing initiatives. Apple gives a reminder to their user and the user will be the whole decision maker whether to continue or not. But google has a closed end approach that within a certain time limit those applications will be inactive. If the user needs to use it further then the user needs to change the settings as well. According to Google they believe that a technology should improve the human life, instead of distracting from it.

More than a humanitarian approach both the companies have their own Artificial Intelligence based products. Such as Apple Home pod and Google Assistant. Recently google launched a new device named Google home hub. All of these products are using huge amount of customer data from various devices such as smartphone wearables etc. By the implementation of the initiatives like digital well-being tech companies can able to enrich user profile with more clear accurate data. Apart from user profiles both the companies are incorporating the parental control as well as family member’s devices to the digital well-being practices. Apple incorporated the parental control settings inside screen time itself but the google implementing it via an app called family link. As a layman, all will give importance to the humanitarian approach by the companies, but here the companies are storing the user data and they are pushing users to buy their new products and services. All of this new services are available only on their newly introduced device that means companies want to gain more market share on their lasts products out there in the market. A company like Google is fetching whole data from a user and creating an enriched profile it will help them to create more targeting advertisement channels and it can be used in business to business applications.

Current Market scenario and statistics

• Browser Market share

Browser	Market share (%)
Chrome	61.51
Safari	15.16
Firefox	5.02
UC Browser	4.42
Opera	3.16
IE	2.87

Figure 3 Data Fetched From Stat Counter Website| Browser Market Share From 2010 to 2018

Google’s Chrome browser is the clear market leader with 63.14% market share. It shows the capabilities and features rich product innovation from Google.

• Mobile OperatingSystem Market share

Operating System	Market share (%)
Android	74.73
iOS	22.32
Kai OS	0.92
Unknown	0.68
Windows	0.36
Samsung	0.30

Figure 4 Data Fetched From Stat Counter Website Mobile OS Market Share From 2010 to 2018

From the above data we can get the current scenario of the mobile phone market that Google’s Android has the core market share and the rest is with Apple.

Android Version	Market share (%)
Marshmallow 6.0	21.02
Nougat 7.0	18.28
Oreo 8.0	16.28
Lollipop 5.1	13.71
Nougat 7.1	10.09
Oreo 8.1	08.79

• **Android Versions Market Share**

Figure 5: Data fetched from stat counter website| Android Version Market share from 2010 to 2018

This data is fetched in October 2018. And a couple of premium smartphones are only featured Android 9.0 Pie at this time. Apart from that, the adoption of the Latest version of Android is not attaining as fast as iOS. People are still using Marshmallow which is three years old as of now. Google wants to covert this units into the latest version.

• **iOS Versions Market share**

iOS Version	Market share (%)
12.0	48.54
11.4	25.64
10.3	5.38
11.2	4.68
11.3	4.04
9.3	3.63

Figure 6 Data Fetched From Stat Counter Website| iOS Versions Market Share From 2010 to 2018

The adoption of Apple products is quite faster than Android products. With the closed source policy Apple is ensuring Software and Hardware sales at the same time.

• **Devices Market Share**

Device	Market share (%)
Mobile	48.2
Desktop	47.78
Tablet	4.03

Figure 7 Data Fetched From Stat Counter Website| Device Market Share From 2010 to 2018

Mobile phones and the desktop are widely using for accessing internet services, as we consider the urgency in information people will definitely rely on Mobile devices. So the potential of mobile devices are more than a Desktop PC. The opportunity for advertisers as well.

• **Search Engine Market Share**

Search Engine	Market share (%)
Google	92.74
Yahoo	2.32
Bing	2.17
Baidu	0.81
Yandex Ru	0.60
CuckDuckGo	0.32

Figure 8 Data Fetched From Stat Counter Website| Search Engine Market Share From 2010 to 2018

Google is the clear market controller in this category. It has more than 90 percent of market share and the rest all other players are very tiny if we compare them with Google. So the data which Google can generate is impeccable. And they want to

use it for Advertisement services, but the latest status on their revenue shows that Google is gradually reducing their reliance on advertisements. That means more product-oriented services like Google home and Pixel will be coming out from Google.

Figure 9 Source: Satisica

Marketing Concerns

Google introduced the Digital Wellbeing practices with a note that they are going to lose the revenue in ad services. But their hardware capabilities both google and apple bring back this threat as an opportunity. With the help of big data and artificial intelligence, both the tech giants are incorporating the data and creating accurate user profiles as well as context-based advertisements as well. Any innovation that has a contextual frame of reference then only it will become more relevant. Currently, online advertisement services are generating a huge amount of money. After the incorporation of contextual based data, the conversion on the online advertisement will improve in an exponential way. According to AppNexus, 0.08% Enhanced Banner Advertisements and 0.08% Custom in Page advertisement is converting as a successful business activity. It shows the importance of creating a more feature rich customer data to classify the customer based on the contextual frame of reference. Digital wellbeing and Screen time initiative is the best example for the industry that how a company can convert a threat into an opportunity.

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